

Neuro-Causal Personality Modeling: Counterfactual Stability Analysis and Cognitive-Semantic Interpretability for MBTI Classification

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Abstract

While transformer-based models achieve strong predictive accuracy in personality modeling, they remain fundamentally opaque, providing no causal account of which linguistic features drive predictions or how stable those predictions are under semantic perturbation. We propose a Neuro-Causal Personality Modeling framework that fuses frozen BERT embeddings with structured psycholinguistic features via a single shared, learnable sigmoid gating function for interpretable, multi-dimensional Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) classification. A counterfactual intervention module, grounded in Pearl’s do-calculus, evaluates prediction robustness under structured feature-level perturbations using Average Probability Shift (APS), Trait Flip Rate (TFR), and Stability Rate (SR) metrics. Experiments across 1,735 test samples reveal that Readability Score and Pronoun Ratio are the dominant causal drivers of MBTI-linked linguistic variation (Mean APS = 0.0331 and 0.0228 respectively at $\lambda = 1.0$), while trait flip rates remain below 7.5% at full intervention magnitude, confirming deterministic model stability. Critically, our analysis shows that the Kaggle MBTI corpus encodes strong lexical identity markers, yet training the shared gated fusion end-to-end yields a hybrid cognitive-semantic representation that outperforms the semantic-only BERT baseline across all four MBTI dimensions, delivering an average Macro-F1 of 0.5351.

Index Terms

Computational personality prediction, Counterfactual intervention, Deep contextual embeddings, MBTI classification, Neuro-causal modeling, Psycholinguistic feature modeling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Personality modeling is at the core of human-centered AI, influencing the design of recommender systems, adaptive learning environments, and digital human analytics [30]. As text data from social media and online communities proliferates, predicting personality from language has emerged as a critical research function [28], [32].

The Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI), comprising four binary dichotomies (I/E, N/S, T/F, J/P), remains a widely adopted framework for describing behavioral patterns in computational contexts [7], [31]. State-of-the-art results have been reported using transformer-based architectures including BERT and its variants [1], ensemble methods combining linguistic features with classical classifiers [2], neural-symbolic integration for personalized learning [3], and large language model approaches [10]. Despite strong predictive performance, these approaches share a fundamental limitation: they are performance-centric black-box systems providing no causal account of which linguistic features drive personality predictions, nor any principled evaluation of prediction stability under semantic perturbation [16], [17].

From a psycholinguistic perspective, language is a transparent window into personality [24], [25]. Features such as pronoun use, modality, negation density, and readability have each been independently linked to personality dimensions in the linguistics literature [12], [26], [27]. However, existing NLP approaches treat these features either as ad hoc engineering choices or ignore them entirely in favor of opaque contextual embeddings. The critical gap is the absence of a causally grounded framework that: (1) explicitly models psycholinguistic features alongside contextual representations, (2) evaluates which features causally drive predictions using Pearl’s do-calculus [11], and (3) assesses prediction robustness through counterfactual interventions [20], [21].

Causal inference has recently emerged as a principled approach to improving the robustness and interpretability of NLP models [19], [20]. Counterfactual explanations offer a theoretically grounded mechanism for probing model behavior without requiring access to internal representations [21]. Yet, to our knowledge, no prior work has applied do-calculus-based counterfactual probing to the psycholinguistic feature space of personality prediction.

This paper presents the *Neuro-Causal Personality Modeling* framework, which addresses these limitations through four primary contributions:

- 1) A **cognitive-semantic dual-pathway architecture** fusing 10-dimensional structured psycholinguistic features [24], [25] with frozen BERT embeddings [5] via a learnable sigmoid gating function for interpretable, multi-dimensional MBTI classification.
- 2) A **counterfactual stability protocol** grounded in Pearl’s do-calculus [11], introducing Average Probability Shift (APS), Trait Flip Rate (TFR), and Stability Rate (SR) as novel evaluation metrics for personality model robustness, which are directly comparable to but theoretically distinct from LIME [13], SHAP [14], and Integrated Gradients [15].
- 3) A **construct versus predictive validity distinction**, representing the first explicit theoretical separation of these evaluation axes in the MBTI NLP literature, grounded in psycholinguistic theory [12], [26] and causal inference principles [19], [20].
- 4) An **empirical dataset critique** revealing that the Kaggle MBTI corpus encodes strong lexical identity markers rather than latent cognitive-semantic personality signals [29], representing a novel empirical finding with implications for the personality computing community.

II. RELATED WORK

Early approaches to personality prediction relied on manually engineered linguistic features with classical classifiers. [2] demonstrated competitive MBTI classification using sentiment, grammatical, and word-level features with hyperparameter-optimized ensemble models. Social media platforms have proven productive for personality research: [29] showed Reddit posts are strong MBTI predictors, while [30] demonstrated automatic personality assessment through Facebook language. [32] established foundational results for personality detection from Twitter text.

Transformer architectures subsequently dominated the field. [7] fine-tuned SimCSE and RoBERTa [33] for MBTI dimension prediction, achieving F1 up to 76.14% on the T/F dimension. [1] and [6] advanced MBTI prediction using enhanced deep learning architectures combining behavioral analysis with NLP approaches. A broader survey by [9] documented BERT-CNN-RNN ensembles achieving up to 85% accuracy. Large language model approaches have recently emerged: [10] introduced the P2P model combining retrieval-augmented generation with fine-tuning. [3] integrated BERT-based MBTI prediction with learner profile ontologies. [4] introduced a fuzzy-logic MBTI model capturing continuous personality expression.

Despite strong predictive performance, these approaches remain performance-centric black-box systems lacking explicit causal grounding, construct validity evaluation, and robustness analysis under semantic perturbation.

A. Explainable AI for NLP

The interpretability of NLP models has attracted significant research attention. [13] introduced LIME, approximating local decision boundaries using token-level perturbations. [14] proposed SHAP, assigning Shapley-value-based feature importance scores. [15] developed Integrated Gradients, an axiomatic attribution method in the gradient space of deep networks. [16] formalized the science of interpretable machine learning, while [17] critically examined its theoretical foundations. [18] provided a comprehensive taxonomy of XAI methods across domains.

A critical limitation shared by LIME [13], SHAP [14], and Integrated Gradients [15] is their operation in the token or embedding space without causal grounding or theoretical feature motivation. None produce stability metrics quantifying prediction robustness under controlled semantic interventions, a gap directly addressed by our APS, TFR, and SR metrics.

B. Causal Inference in Machine Learning

The intersection of causal inference and machine learning has emerged as a productive frontier. [19] provided a comprehensive overview of causal representation learning, relating Pearl’s causal hierarchy [11] to transfer learning and generalization. [22] established the theoretical foundations of causal inference for machine learning through structural causal models.

In NLP specifically, [20] provided the first unified survey of causal inference methods for language processing. [23] introduced CausaLM, producing counterfactual explanations through adversarial fine-tuning. [21] established theoretical and legal foundations for counterfactual explanations in automated decision-making.

Despite these advances, causal inference methods have not been applied to the psycholinguistic feature space of personality prediction, a gap our framework explicitly addresses.

C. Psycholinguistic Feature Modeling

The relationship between language use and personality has a rich empirical tradition. [24] developed LIWC, the foundational psycholinguistic dictionary mapping word categories to psychological states. [25] validated LIWC’s detection of individual differences across diverse experimental settings. [26] demonstrated that function words, particularly pronouns, reliably reflect psychological states. [27] established linguistic style as a stable individual difference measure. At scale, [28] showed social media language robustly predicts personality dimensions. [12] demonstrated automatic personality recognition from conversation and text using linguistically motivated features, representing the most directly related prior work to our cognitive feature pathway.

Despite this rich tradition, psycholinguistic features have not been integrated with causal inference frameworks for personality modeling, a gap directly addressed by the proposed framework, in contrast to autoregressive approaches such as XLNet [34].

D. Positioning of the Proposed Framework

The proposed Neuro-Causal Personality Modeling framework is, to our knowledge, the first to simultaneously: (1) ground personality prediction in psycholinguistic theory [24]–[26]; (2) apply Pearl’s do-calculus [11] counterfactual interventions to the cognitive feature space; (3) introduce dedicated stability metrics (APS, TFR, SR) for robustness evaluation; and (4) provide an empirical critique of the Kaggle MBTI corpus through a construct validity lens [12], contributing to both the computational personality [20] and causal NLP [19] communities.

Fig. 1. System architecture.

III. PROPOSED NEURO-CAUSAL HYBRID FRAMEWORK

The overall framework essentially ties together two different representational pathways, one *cognitive feature pathway* and one *semantic encoding pathway*, into a single neuro-causal setup that is well-suited to transparent MBTI predictions. You can see the overall structure of the model laid out in Figure 1.

The overall architecture of the model is composed of eight different modules, each of which is crucial to the overall process. These modules are:

- 1) **Input Layer:** This layer accepts the raw, free-form text input into the model.
- 2) **Preprocessing:** This module handles the overall preprocessing of the input, including tokenization and handling of punctuation and stopwords.
- 3) **Cognitive Feature Path:** This module handles the overall extraction of cognitive features from the input text.
- 4) **Semantic Encoding Path:** This module handles the overall encoding of the input text using the BERT model.
- 5) **Hybrid Fusion Layer:** This module combines the two projected representations using a shared, learned sigmoid gating mechanism, producing a consistent joint vector \mathbf{J} .
- 6) **Multi-Dimensional MBTI Classifier:** This module is composed of an optional two-layer MLP trunk followed by four binary classifiers, one each for the IE, NS, TF, and JP dimensions of the

MBTI model.

- 7) **Counterfactual Engine:** This module handles the overall generation of counterfactuals using do-calculus.
- 8) **Generative Explanation Layer:** This module handles the overall generation of explanations, conditioned upon the fused representations and the overall prediction result

A. Data Flow and Processing Pipeline

The overall pipeline is illustrated in Figure 2. Processing begins with normalized, tokenized text, which is routed in parallel to the cognitive feature extraction module and the frozen BERT encoder. The two resulting representations are fused via the sigmoid gate and forwarded to the multi-task classifier. Counterfactual generation is applied post-hoc as an optional interpretability step, producing APS and TFR metrics for the classified sample.

Fig. 2. Data flow and processing pipeline.

The pipeline is modular: each stage exposes a well-defined interface enabling isolated evaluation and ablation. At inference time, classification executes in a single forward pass; counterfactual generation is invoked as an optional post-hoc step.

TABLE I

COGNITIVE FEATURE DEFINITIONS DERIVED FROM IMPLEMENTATION. N_j : VALID TOKEN COUNT; α_j : ALPHABETIC TOKENS; \mathcal{M} : MODAL LEMMAS; \mathcal{E}_{NRC} : NRC EMOTION LEXICON; $N_w, N_s, N_{\text{syll}}$: WORD, SENTENCE, SYLLABLE COUNTS; \mathcal{U} : UNCERTAINTY LEMMAS {UNSURE, MIGHT, MAYBE}.

c_i	Feature	Mathematical Definition	Agg.
c_1	Pronoun Ratio	$\frac{\sum_{t \in s_j} \mathbb{1}[\text{pos}_t = \text{PRON}]}{N_j}$	Mean
c_2	Modality Score	$\frac{\sum_{t \in s_j} \mathbb{1}[\text{lemma}_t \in \mathcal{M}]}{N_j}$	Mean
c_3	Negation Count	$\sum_{t \in s_j} \mathbb{1}[\text{dep}_t = \text{neg}]$	Var
c_4	Uncertainty Marker	$\mathbb{1}[\exists t : \text{lemma}_t \in \mathcal{U}]$	Prop
c_5	Emotion Intensity	$\frac{\sum_{t \in s_j} \mathbb{1}[\text{lemma}_t \in \mathcal{E}_{\text{NRC}}]}{N_j}$	Mean
c_6	Lexical Diversity	$\frac{ \{\text{lower}(t) : t \in \alpha_j\} }{ \alpha_j }$	Mean
c_7	Readability (FRE)	$206.835 - 1.015 \frac{N_w}{N_s} - 84.6 \frac{N_{\text{syll}}}{N_w}$	Mean
c_8	Sentence Length	$ s_j $	Var
c_9	Reasoning Marker	$\mathbb{1}[\exists t : \text{lemma}_t \in \{\text{because, therefore, if}\}]$	Prop
c_{10}	Planning Marker	$\mathbb{1}[\exists t : \text{lemma}_t \in \{\text{plan, decide, goal}\}]$	Prop

B. Cognitive Feature Modeling

Let x denote an input text composed of T sentences $\{s_j\}_{j=1}^T$. For each sentence s_j , let N_j denote the total number of valid (non-whitespace) tokens, and let α_j denote the subset of alphabetic tokens. The cognitive extraction function $\phi_{\text{cog}} : \mathcal{V}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ maps x to

$$\mathbf{C} = \phi_{\text{cog}}(x) = [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{10}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{10}. \quad (1)$$

All ten features are formally defined in Table I. Sentence-level values are aggregated to document level using three rules: ratio-based features (c_1 – c_2 , c_5 – c_7) are averaged ($\bar{c} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_j c(s_j)$); count-based features (c_3 , c_8) use population variance ($\sigma_c^2 = \frac{1}{T} \sum_j (c(s_j) - \bar{c})^2$); and binary markers (c_4 , c_9 – c_{10}) use proportion ($\hat{p} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_j \mathbb{1}[c(s_j) = 1]$).

After aggregation, the resulting document-level keys are

$\{c_{1,\text{mean}}, c_{2,\text{mean}}, c_{3,\text{var}}, c_{4,\text{prop}}, c_{5,\text{mean}}, c_{6,\text{mean}}, c_{7,\text{mean}}, c_{8,\text{var}}, c_{9,\text{prop}}, c_{10,\text{prop}}\}$, concatenated into the 10-dimensional cognitive vector $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{R}^{10}$.

C. Semantic Encoding (BERT Path)

Parallel to the cognitive path, the semantic encoder applies a pre-trained BERT [5] model:

$$\mathbf{H}_{\text{seq}} = \text{BERT}(x) = [\mathbf{h}_{[\text{CLS}]}, \mathbf{h}_1, \dots, \mathbf{h}_L] \in \mathbb{R}^{(L+1) \times d}, \quad (2)$$

where L is the token count and $d = 768$. The document embedding is obtained via mean pooling:

$$\mathbf{H} = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{i=1}^L \mathbf{h}_i \in \mathbb{R}^d. \quad (3)$$

Mean pooling distributes representational weight evenly, yielding stable sentence embeddings [8] that capture discourse-level semantics complementary to \mathbf{C} .

D. Structured Hybrid Fusion Layer

A critical design requirement is that the fusion function operates with a *single, shared* set of parameters across the entire dataset. Prior to fusion, both the cognitive vector $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{R}^{10}$ and the semantic vector $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{768}$ are projected into a shared space \mathbb{R}^{512} via independent learned linear maps with Layer Normalisation:

$$\hat{\mathbf{C}} = \text{LN}(\mathbf{W}_c \mathbf{C} + \mathbf{b}_c), \quad \hat{\mathbf{H}} = \text{LN}(\mathbf{W}_s \mathbf{H} + \mathbf{b}_s). \quad (4)$$

The two normalised projections are concatenated and passed through a learned sigmoid gate that controls the element-wise contribution of each pathway:

$$\mathbf{g} = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_g [\hat{\mathbf{C}}; \hat{\mathbf{H}}] + \mathbf{b}_g) \in \mathbb{R}^{512}. \quad (5)$$

The fused representation is then:

$$\mathbf{J} = \mathbf{g} \odot \hat{\mathbf{C}} + (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{g}) \odot \hat{\mathbf{H}} \in \mathbb{R}^{512}, \quad (6)$$

where \odot denotes element-wise multiplication. Because the gate parameters are shared across all documents and optimized end-to-end, every sample is projected through an identical transformation yielding a semantically consistent manifold.

E. Multi-Dimensional MBTI Classification

The `HybridMBTIModel` stacks the shared gating module with an optional two-layer GELU MLP trunk (hidden dimension 384, dropout 0.2) followed by a Layer Normalisation, branching into four independent linear heads (I/E, N/S, T/F, J/P):

$$\mathbf{h} = \text{LN}(\text{MLP}(\mathbf{J})), \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{y}_d = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_d \mathbf{h} + b_d), \quad d \in \{\text{IE}, \text{NS}, \text{TF}, \text{JP}\}, \quad (8)$$

with threshold decision $\tilde{y}_d = \mathbb{1}[\hat{y}_d \geq 0.5]$. Training minimises independent binary cross-entropy losses:

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_d \mathcal{L}_{\text{BCE}}(\hat{y}_d, y_d^*). \quad (9)$$

The full MBTI type is reconstructed by concatenating $[\tilde{y}_{\text{IE}}, \tilde{y}_{\text{NS}}, \tilde{y}_{\text{TF}}, \tilde{y}_{\text{JP}}]$, yielding one of 16 types.

F. Causal Interaction Modeling

Figure 3 presents the causal Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG).

The relationship between inputs and MBTI dimensions is formalized as a Structural Causal Model (SCM) [11]. The structural equation for the d -th dimension is

$$Y_d = f_d(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{H}, \varepsilon_d), \quad (10)$$

where ε_d is exogenous noise and f_d is parameterized by $\{\mathbf{W}_d, b_d\}$. To assess the causal effect of feature C_i , Pearl's do-operator sets $C_i \leftarrow c'_i$ while fixing all other variables:

$$\Pr(Y_d \mid \text{do}(C_i = c'_i)) = \Pr(Y_d \mid C_i = c'_i) \Big|_{\text{graph truncated at } C_i}. \quad (11)$$

Fig. 3. Causal interaction DAG.

Algorithm 1 Feature-level do-intervention for counterfactual generation

Require: Cognitive vector C ; semantic vector H ; intervention set $\mathcal{S} = \{(\text{feat}_k, x_{\text{ref},k}, \lambda_k)\}$ with $\lambda_k \in [0.2, 0.4]$.

Ensure: Counterfactual predictions \hat{y}_{cf} .

- 1: $C_{\text{cf}} \leftarrow C.\text{clone}()$
 - 2: **for each** $(\text{feat}_k, x_{\text{ref},k}, \lambda_k) \in \mathcal{S}$ **do**
 - 3: $i \leftarrow \text{index}(\text{feat}_k)$
 - 4: $x \leftarrow C_{\text{cf},i}$
 - 5: $C_{\text{cf},i} \leftarrow x + \lambda_k (x_{\text{ref},k} - x)$ {deterministic relative shift}
 - 6: **end for**
 - 7: $\hat{C}_{\text{cf}} \leftarrow \mathbf{W}_{\text{proj}} C_{\text{cf}} + \mathbf{b}_{\text{proj}}$
 - 8: $\mathbf{g}_{\text{cf}} \leftarrow \sigma(\mathbf{W}_g [\hat{C}_{\text{cf}}; \hat{H}] + \mathbf{b}_g)$
 - 9: $\mathbf{J}_{\text{cf}} \leftarrow \mathbf{g}_{\text{cf}} \odot \hat{C}_{\text{cf}} + (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{g}_{\text{cf}}) \odot \hat{H}$
 - 10: $\hat{y}_{\text{cf}} \leftarrow \{\sigma(\mathbf{W}_d \mathbf{J}_{\text{cf}} + b_d)\}_d$
 - 11: **return** \hat{y}_{cf}
-

Algorithm 2 Counterfactual Trait-Flip Decision

Require: Factual probabilities \hat{y} ; counterfactual probabilities \hat{y}_{cf} .

Ensure: Trait-flip indicators $\{f_d\}_d$.

```

1: for each dimension  $d$  do
2:    $p \leftarrow \hat{y}_d$ ;  $p_{cf} \leftarrow \hat{y}_{cf,d}$ 
3:   if  $(p \geq 0.6 \wedge p_{cf} \leq 0.4)$  or  $(p \leq 0.4 \wedge p_{cf} \geq 0.6)$  then
4:      $f_d \leftarrow 1$  {trait flip detected}
5:   else
6:      $f_d \leftarrow 0$  {buffer zone (0.4, 0.6): no flip}
7:   end if
8: end for
9: return  $\{f_d\}_d$ 

```

G. Counterfactual Stability Analysis

Counterfactual stability analysis probes prediction robustness via structured do-calculus perturbations. Algorithm 1 describes the feature-level intervention; Algorithm 2 formalizes the trait-flip decision.

The intervention formula (Algorithm 1, line 5) is

$$x_{cf} = x + \lambda(x_{ref} - x), \quad \lambda \in [0.2, 0.4], \quad (12)$$

a deterministic relative shift that moves feature C_i a fraction λ of the distance toward a reference value x_{ref} , with the semantic vector \mathbf{H} held fixed throughout. A trait flip is declared when the factual and counterfactual probabilities fall on opposite sides of the buffer zone $[0.4, 0.6]$ (Algorithm 2, lines 3–7).

H. Generative Explanation Layer

The explanation layer synthesizes a human-readable interpretation of the classification outcome and counterfactual analysis. Given the fused representation \mathbf{J} , the predicted type $\tilde{y} = [\tilde{y}_{IE}, \tilde{y}_{NS}, \tilde{y}_{TF}, \tilde{y}_{JP}]$, the counterfactual feature deltas $\Delta\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{C}_{cf} - \mathbf{C}$, and the cognitive vector \mathbf{C} , the explanation function \mathcal{G} produces

$$\mathcal{E} = \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{J}, \tilde{y}, \Delta\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{C}). \quad (13)$$

\mathcal{E} is a template-grounded narrative conditioned on the top contributing cognitive features (ranked by $|\Delta C_i|$) and their psycholinguistic interpretation. For example, a high pronoun ratio c_1 coupled with low modality score c_2 may yield: “*Frequent first-person references with limited hedging language are associated with an Extraverted and Thinking profile.*” The explanation layer closes the interpretability loop by grounding predictions in identifiable linguistic evidence and quantifying feature-level sensitivity.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Dataset

Experiments were conducted on the publicly available MBTI dataset sourced from Kaggle (initially compiled from PersonalityCafe). To address ethical considerations and prevent data leakage, explicitly identifiable Reddit artifacts ($u/$, $r/$) and explicit MBTI class indicators were systematically removed, alongside baseline noise such as HTML tags and URLs. Since class distribution is naturally imbalanced, the training set was balanced using deterministic rule-based augmentation. The dataset was split into 80% for training and 20% for testing, stratifying on all 16 classes to preserve class distribution. Summary statistics are provided in Table II.

TABLE II
DATASET STATISTICS AND CHARACTERISTICS

Statistic	Value
Total Samples	8,675
MBTI Classes	16
Avg. Text Length	~1,242.8 words
Train/Test Split	80/20 (Stratified)
Imbalance Handling	Deterministic Rule-based Augmentation

B. Implementation Details

We implemented our experiments using PyTorch and Scikit-Learn libraries. The semantic representations are based on a frozen `bert-base-cased` model to produce 768-dimensional vectors. A single shared instance of `GatedFusion` seeded with `torch.manual_seed(42)` was deployed. We combined cognitive and semantic features into a common 512-dimensional space using layer-normalized projections and combined them via the learned shared sigmoid gate.

End-to-end training of the `HybridMBTIModel` was performed with AdamW ($\text{lr} = 3 \times 10^{-4}$, weight decay 10^{-4}), class-balanced `BCEWithLogitsLoss`, up to 80 epochs with early stopping (patience 15). For full reproducibility of all scripts, we set a global random seed to 42.

Counterfactual interventions were strictly executed at the feature-level mapping ($x_{cf} = x + \lambda(x_{ref} - x)$). Intervention magnitudes (λ) were limited to $[0.2, 0.4]$ for active prediction thresholds, and extended to $\lambda \in \{0.3, 0.5, 1.0\}$ for systematic scale-sweeps.

C. Evaluation Protocol

Due to underlying class imbalances and the structure of the four binary MBTI tasks, predictive performance was exclusively evaluated using macro-averaged metrics. The complete evaluation suite consists of Macro-F1 (primary objective), Macro-Precision, Macro-Recall, and ROC-AUC. Confusion matrices and threshold-independent ROC curves were analyzed to evaluate classification behavior across decision thresholds.

We validated the complementary fusion hypothesis through a structured ablation study, contrasting the fully consolidated joint representation against an isolated cognitive-only configuration and a semantic-only BERT baseline. Finally, inference stability limits under active causal intervention were quantified over the independent test set utilizing task-specific stability metrics: Average Probability Shift (APS), corresponding Trait Flip Rates (TFR), and overall Stability Rate (SR).

D. Prototype Interface

To demonstrate end-to-end operability of the proposed Neuro-Causal framework, a lightweight web-based prototype was developed and deployed locally using a React front-end (Vite) communicating with a Flask REST API back-end. The prototype exposes the complete inference pipeline, including cognitive feature extraction, semantic BERT encoding, sigmoid-gated fusion, multi-dimensional MBTI classification, sentence-level attribution, and counterfactual analysis, through a three-stage interactive interface.

Stage 1: Text Input. As shown in Fig. 4, the landing page presents a free-form text entry field prompting users to describe their thinking style, decision-making preferences, and typical behaviors. A real-time word counter validates the minimum length requirement (150 words), displaying a “*Minimum met*” confirmation and recommending 200–300 words for optimal model reliability. Submission triggers a single REST call that invokes the full feature extraction and classification pipeline on the server.

Stage 2: Prediction and Causal Attribution Results. Fig. 5 displays the primary results page returned after inference. The panel comprises four integrated components: (i) the predicted MBTI type and overall

Fig. 4. Prototype input interface.

confidence score (e.g., ENFJ at 54.5%); (ii) a horizontal bar chart reporting the per-dimension classification probabilities for all four MBTI dichotomies (I/E, N/S, T/F, J/P); (iii) a radar chart visualizing the normalized values of all ten cognitive features (c_1-c_{10}) as defined in Section III-B, providing an immediate psycholinguistic fingerprint of the submitted text; and (iv) a sentence-level attribution list ranked by causal contribution weight, which directly reflects the do-calculus sensitivity analysis described in Section III-G. A template-grounded natural-language *Explanation* paragraph closes the panel, summarizing the dominant linguistic drivers of the predicted personality profile.

Stage 3: Interactive Counterfactual Analysis. Fig. 6 illustrates the counterfactual analysis panel, which implements the do-calculus intervention module described in Section III-G as an interactive tool. The user selects an intervention feature (e.g., Pronoun Usage) from a dropdown menu and adjusts the intervention strength λ via a continuous slider (0 = factual, 1 = strong intervention). The interface renders the factual and counterfactual MBTI predictions side-by-side, accompanied by dual probability bar charts for direct comparison. The lower portion reports the per-dimension probability shift (ΔP), per-feature trait sensitivity scores, and a trait-flip stability indicator for each MBTI dimension (Stable / Flipped), governed by the threshold rule $P \geq 0.6 \leftrightarrow P \leq 0.4$. A counterfactual explanation paragraph contextualizes the causal shift in natural language, enabling practitioners to interrogate model sensitivity and validate prediction robustness without requiring programmatic access to the underlying pipeline.

Together, the three interface stages confirm that the framework’s causal and interpretability components are accessible to non-expert users, meeting the transparency and usability objectives stated in Section III.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Construct Validity vs. Predictive Validity

We distinguish two complementary evaluation axes throughout this section. *Predictive validity* concerns whether the model correctly classifies known MBTI labels; *construct validity* concerns whether the features used reflect authentic, theoretically grounded personality constructs [12]. Our cognitive feature pathway is grounded in psycholinguistic theory, where pronoun ratio, modality, negation, and readability are each linked to personality dimensions in the linguistics literature. Our counterfactual analysis evaluates whether

Fig. 5. Prediction results interface.

Fig. 6. Counterfactual analysis interface.

these theoretically motivated features causally drive predictions, independent of surface label accuracy. This construct validity lens is particularly appropriate for the Kaggle MBTI corpus, where ground-truth labels are unvalidated community self-reports rather than clinically administered assessments. We report both axes explicitly in the following subsections, presenting the counterfactual (construct) analysis before the predictive (accuracy) analysis.

B. Counterfactual Stability Analysis

Counterfactual stability is evaluated per MBTI dimension using APS, TFR, and SR under single-feature do-calculus interventions ($n = 1,735$ test samples). Table III reports dimension-wise metrics at operational $\lambda = 0.3$, confirming high stability across all dichotomies (Mean SR = 0.9932). The TF dimension exhibits the highest susceptibility (APS = 0.0117), consistent with its sensitivity to pronoun-level variation identified in Section V-C.

TABLE III
DIMENSION-WISE STABILITY UNDER PRONOUN RATIO INTERVENTION ($\lambda = 0.3$, $n = 1,735$)

Dimension	APS ↓	TFR (%) ↓	SR ↑
IE	0.0018	0.29	0.9982
NS	0.0062	0.98	0.9938
TF	0.0117	2.07	0.9883
JP	0.0075	2.07	0.9925
Mean	0.0068	1.35	0.9932

Table IV extends this analysis across all ten cognitive features at maximal intervention ($\lambda = 1.0$), providing a complete per-dimension causal sensitivity profile directly grounded in project-computed values. The TF dimension is consistently the most sensitive across all features. Pronoun Ratio achieves APS = 0.0395 on TF, confirming that first-person reference density is a strong causal driver of Thinking/Feeling classification. IE and JP exhibit comparatively stable behavior, indicating that structural markers exert dimension-specific rather than uniform causal influence.

TABLE IV
PER-DIMENSION AVERAGE PROBABILITY SHIFT (APS) AT $\lambda = 1.0$ FOR TOP COGNITIVE FEATURES

Feature	IE	NS	TF	JP	Mean
Readability Score	0.0194	0.0466	0.0284	0.0381	0.0331
Pronoun Ratio	0.0061	0.0208	0.0395	0.0249	0.0228
Lexical Diversity	0.0136	0.0123	0.0372	0.0011	0.0161
Negation Count	0.0175	0.0024	0.0307	0.0122	0.0157
Planning Marker	0.0029	0.0121	0.0243	0.0206	0.0150
Modality Score	0.0118	0.0061	0.0285	0.0068	0.0133
Uncertainty (c_4)	0.0219	0.0010	0.0235	0.0064	0.0132
Reasoning Marker	0.0009	0.0148	0.0169	0.0010	0.0084
Sentence Length	0.0059	0.0073	0.0012	0.0001	0.0036
Emotion Intensity	0.0109	0.0051	0.0227	0.0053	0.0110

The stability threshold curve (Figure 7) confirms that trait inversions occur at highly predictable, restricted thresholds, establishing deterministic model stability independent of stochastic noise. Emotion Intensity records the lowest mean APS = 0.0110 among all features, indicating that affective features exert minimal causal influence on the decision boundary, substantially less than structural and stylistic features, a finding consistent with the surface-pattern hypothesis for the Kaggle MBTI corpus.

Fig. 7. Stability threshold curve: Probability Shift (APS) vs. Intervention magnitude (λ).

TABLE V
COMPARISON OF EXPLAINABILITY METHODS FOR NLP PERSONALITY PREDICTION

Method	Causal Grounding	Feature Space	Theory-Driven	Stability Metric
LIME [13]	No	Token / superpixel	No	None
SHAP	No	Any input features	No	None
Integrated Gradients	No	Embedding dimensions	No	None
Ours (do-calculus)	Yes	Psycholinguistic features	Yes	APS, TFR, SR

C. Cognitive Attribution and Causal Ranking

Feature attribution is derived via causal sensitivity analysis: each cognitive feature is independently intervened upon at $\lambda = 1.0$, and the resulting mean APS is treated as its causal importance score. As shown in Figure 8, the dominant contributors are Readability Score (APS = 0.0331), Pronoun Ratio (APS = 0.0228), and Lexical Diversity (APS = 0.0161). Affective features such as Emotion Intensity record the lowest mean APS = 0.0110, indicating minimal sensitivity relative to structural features, consistent with the surface-pattern hypothesis for the Kaggle corpus.

Unlike token-level attribution methods such as LIME [13] or gradient-based approaches such as Integrated Gradients, our causal sensitivity analysis operates directly in the theoretically grounded psycholinguistic feature space using Pearl’s do-calculus [11]. Table V summarizes the key distinctions between our approach and existing interpretability methods.

D. Predictive Performance and Hybrid Comparison

A structured ablation study compares the joint fused framework against its constituent modalities. As summarized in Table VI, the end-to-end trained `HybridMBTIModel` achieves the highest average Macro-F1 (0.5351), outperforming both the Semantic-only (BERT) baseline (0.5222) by +0.0129 and the Cognitive-only configuration (0.4320). The shared deterministic gating allows the model to consistently combine structured linguistic features with the high-dimensional BERT semantic space, resolving previous

Fig. 8. Feature Importance Heatmap: Causal Sensitivity (APS) across features and MBTI dimensions.

empirical limitations where naïve fusion setups suppressed peak semantic performance. Our counterfactual analysis, operating on the theoretically motivated cognitive feature pathway, therefore constitutes a construct validity probe rather than just a predictive evaluation, reinforcing that the public domain MBTI dataset encodes lexical structure heavily, yet the hybrid fusion successfully captures complementary predictive signals.

TABLE VI
PREDICTIVE PERFORMANCE AND ABLATION ON MACRO-F1 (N = 1,735 TEST SAMPLES)

Configuration	IE F1	NS F1	TF F1	JP F1	Avg Macro-F1
Cognitive-only	0.4591	0.3069	0.5755	0.3864	0.4320
Semantic-only (BERT)	0.5131	0.4805	0.5813	0.5141	0.5222
Joint Fused (LR on trained J)	0.5036	0.5149	0.5838	0.5258	0.5320
Hybrid Trained (end-to-end)	0.5146	0.5119	0.5867	0.5271	0.5351

The confusion matrices (Figure 9) and ROC curves (Figure 10) confirm balanced tradeoffs across all four dimensions (Joint Fused: Macro-Precision = 0.5320, Macro-Recall = 0.5327, AUC = 0.5523).

E. Gate Weight Analysis

Post-training inspection of the learned sigmoid gate $\mathbf{g} \in \mathbb{R}^{512}$ provides an additional interpretability signal beyond counterfactual analysis. The gate consistently assigns higher mean weight to the semantic pathway ($\bar{g} \approx 0.72$ – 0.75 across test samples), confirming that frozen BERT representations dominate the fused representation \mathbf{J} . However, for samples exhibiting high pronoun ratio c_1 or strong planning marker

Fig. 9. Aggregate Confusion Matrices for all four MBTI classification dimensions.

Fig. 10. ROC Curves: True Positive vs. False Positive tradeoff per MBTI dimension.

presence c_{10} , the cognitive pathway contribution exceeds 0.30, indicating that structured linguistic features activate selectively under cognitively salient text conditions. This input-dependent gating behaviour links individual cognitive features to their dynamic contribution to final classification, providing a complementary interpretability layer that operates at the fusion level rather than requiring post-hoc perturbation.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work establishes three empirical contributions to cognitive-semantic personality modeling. First, a *neuro-causal fusion architecture* grounds MBTI prediction in psycholinguistic theory via a single shared, learnable sigmoid-gated integration of frozen BERT embeddings ($d = 768$) with 10-dimensional structured cognitive features. Second, a *counterfactual stability protocol* operationalizes construct validity through Pearl’s do-calculus interventions, quantifying causal feature influence via APS, TFR, and SR across all four MBTI dimensions. Third, an *empirical dataset critique* reveals that the Kaggle MBTI corpus encodes strong lexical identity markers, motivating robust architectures capable of leveraging both cognitive and deep embeddings effectively.

Experiments on 1,735 test samples confirm that Readability Score (APS=0.0331) and Pronoun Ratio (APS=0.0228) are the dominant causal drivers of personality-linked linguistic variation, with the TF dimension exhibiting the highest sensitivity to cognitive feature perturbations (Pronoun Ratio APS=0.0395 at $\lambda = 1.0$). Trait flip rates remain below 7.5% at full intervention magnitude ($\lambda = 1.0$), confirming deterministic model stability. The framework achieves an average Macro-F1 of 0.5351, outperforming standalone semantic models with complete causal attribution and stability evaluation; in context, this confirms that structured psycholinguistic features, when properly fused through a consistent learned gate, provide complementary signal beyond that of contextual embeddings alone.

Future work will apply this framework to clinically validated personality datasets such as the Essays corpus [12] and PAN-2015 Author Profiling, and extend counterfactual interventions to multimodal behavioral signals to address the ecological validity gap in personality computing. Richer structural causal models will enable continuous personality trait analysis beyond binary MBTI dichotomies.

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